

CATEGORY – COMMUNITY, LIVELIHOOD

LANGUAGE – NORTHERN SAMI

Guođoheapmi

Ovttasbargu
ja vuorrováikkuhus

Ealáhusaid
mánnggahápmásašvuohta

Gárdebiebman

Miessemearkun

Gárdeguotteheapmi

Čohkkemat
ja rátkimat

Njuovvan

Guohtoneatnamiid
johtinmolsun

Fuođđariid
buvttadeapmi

Leverage from
the EU
2014–2020

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Boazobargiid mearri,
váldo- ja
oalgedoaibmasašvuhta,
ahke- ja
sohkabeallejuohkáseapmi

Boazobargiid
buresbirgen

Bohccuid
dearvvašvuoda dikšun

Kultuvra, árvvut
ja identiteahtta

Árbevirolaš diehtu;
Skuvlen

Teknologiija

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the EU
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CATEGORY – CLIMATE, ENVIRONMENT

LANGUAGE – NORTHERN SAMI

Guottet

Ragat

Spirenálit

Boazonálli
ja bohccuid
buresbirgen

Gidđadálki;
Muohhtaga suddan;
Šaddanbaji álgu

Geassedálki;
Bálggádat;
Vistta

Čakčadálki;
Buolašteapmi/
muohttán/
jiekŋugoahhtin

Dálvedálki;
Muohhtadilit

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CATEGORY – LAND USE

LANGUAGE – NORTHERN SAMI

Eanandoallu

Vuovdedoallu

Golleroggan

Ruvkedoaibma

Darfebuvttadeapmi

Čáhcefápmu

Bieggafápmu

Infrastrukturvra
ja ássan

Luopmoássan

Geasseguohtumat

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CATEGORY – LAND USE

LANGUAGE – NORTHERN SAMI

Dálveguohtumat

Luonddusuodjalanguovllut
ja luonddu
áhpásnuvvangeavahus

Meahccebivdu;
Beatnagat

Rábbegovvádus

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the EU
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CATEGORY – SOCIETY, ECONOMY, GOVERNANCE

LANGUAGE – NORTHERN SAMI

Boazodoalu imago

Boazobuktagiid
beaggin

Eamiálbmogiid
rievttit

Riikkaidgaskasaš
soahpamušat

Eanangeavahusa
plánen

Biergomárkanat

Álbmotlaš
láhkaásaheapmi

Gánnáhahttivuohta
ja golut

Doarjagat
ja buhtadusat

Doaibmiid
gaskavuoda
luohttámuš

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CATEGORY – JOKERS, SURPRISES

Dálkkádatrievdan;
Dálkki
ravdafenomenat

Dálkkádatrievdama
vuoimmálaš goahcan;
Ruoná doajáhat

Pandemiijaid áigi

Geopolitihkalaš dilli

LANGUAGE – NORTHERN SAMI

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